

Studies on some Benzimidazole Derivatives as Antibacterial Agents. Part-I. Antibacterial Activities of some Sulphonamidobenzimidazole Derivatives

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Antibacterial activities of some sulphonamides derived from amino acids and peptides and the corresponding sulphonamidobenzimidazole derivatives have been studied for two gram-positive bacteria, viz., *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and two gram-negative bacteria, viz., *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli*. While the parent sulphonamides were devoid of any measurable activity, the corresponding sulphonamidobenzimidazoles showed considerable antibacterial actions for all the four bacteria.

ANTIBACTERIAL, fungicidal, insecticidal, anti-helmentic, virucidal and tuberculostatic activities have been reported for many benzimidazole derivatives¹⁻¹². Sulphanilamide and other substituted sulphonamides are known to inhibit the growth of many bacteria^{13,14}. In the present paper we report the results of our study on the effects of some sulphonamides derived from some essential aminoacids and peptides and those of the corresponding sulphonamidobenzimidazole derivatives (compounds 1-6, Table 1) on the growth of two gram-positive bacteria, viz., *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA) and *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (BA), and two gram-negative bacteria, viz., *Salmonella typhi* (ST) and *Escherichia coli* (EC). Similar study has also been made with 4[2-benzimidazolylmethylamino]-4-oxobutanoic acid and 4-[2-benzimidazolylmethylamino]-4-oxobut-2-(*cis*)enoic acid (compounds 7 and 8, Table 1), where R₁ = H, but R₂ = NHCOCH₂-CH₂COOH and NHCOCH=CHCOOH respectively, though they do not belong to the same class as compounds 1-6.

Experimental

Materials : Compounds 4 and 5 have been newly synthesised by condensing-*o*-phenylenediamine with *N*-benzenesulphonylglycylglycine and *N-p*-toluenesulphonylglycylglycine, respectively by fusion method^{15,16}. Compound 7 has been synthesised from succinic anhydride and 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole following an analogous procedure as applied in the synthesis of compound 8 from maleic anhydride and 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole¹⁷. All the other sulphonamidobenzimidazoles and the parent sulphonylamino acid and peptide derivatives were prepared by the reported procedures^{18,19}, and their purity were confirmed by checking the melting points. All the compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, and uv, ir and mass spectral measurements.

Methods : Antibacterial activities were tested by serial tube dilution method²⁰. The inoculations of the strains of bacteria, viz., SA, BA, ST and EC were prepared in previously sterilised identical

TABLE 1—SULPHONAMIDOBENZIMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES

Compd. no.	Sulphonamidobenzimidazoles		
		R ₁	R ₂
1.	2-[<i>N</i> -Benzenesulphonylamino]methylbenzimidazole	H	NHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₅
2.	2-[<i>N-p</i> -Toluenesulphonylamino]methylbenzimidazole	H	NHSO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ , <i>p</i>
3.	2-[Benzenesulphonylamino]ethylbenzimidazole	H	CH ₂ -NHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₅
4.	<i>N</i> -Benzenesulphonylglycyl- <i>N'</i> -(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)-amide	H	NHCOCH ₂ NHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₅
5.	<i>N-p</i> -Toluenesulphonylglycyl- <i>N'</i> -(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)-amide	H	NHCOCH ₂ NHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ , <i>p</i>
6.	2-(1'-Benzenesulphonylamino-3'-methylmercapto)propylbenzimidazole	CH ₂ CH ₂ SCH ₃	NHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₅
7.	4-[2-Benzimidazolylmethylamino]-4-oxobutanoic acid	H	NHCOCH ₂ CH ₂ COOH
8.	4-[2-Benzimidazolylmethylamino]-4-oxobut-2-(<i>cis</i>)enoic acid	H	NHCOCH=CHCOOH

assay tubes and were allowed to grow in the nutrient broth medium at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ (thermostated) for 24 h both in the absence and in the presence of different concentrations the inhibitors (*i.e.* compounds 1-8). The resultant turbidities were measured at 590 nm with the help of a spectrophotometer. The results of variation of bacterial growth inhibition as a function of inhibitor concentration are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE OF INHIBITION OF BACTERIAL GROWTH

Compd. no.	Concentration $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Temp. = $37 \pm 0.05^\circ$; pH = 7.0			
		SA	BA	ST	EC
1.	300	67	ti*	78	ti*
	250	43	53	58	61
	200	30	27	42	37
	125	13	11	23	15
2.	300	71	86	95	ti*
	250	49	58	58	64
	200	36	39	35	22
	125	17	19	10	5
3.	300	50	52	65	64
	250	36	46	50	55
	200	26	34	42	51
	125	14	22	31	47
4.	300	79	86	95	ti*
	250	65	59	66	76
	200	59	47	48	68
	125	50	32	27	56
5.	75	84	72	ti*	89
	50	56	47	56	64
	25	43	32	21	46
	12.5	26	10	8	28
6.	75	74	72	61	65
	50	49	47	51	45
	25	30	22	31	22
	12.5	18	10	22	11
7.	300	43	47	48	64
	250	28	34	33	43
	200	25	27	22	32
	125	18	18	13	18
8.	300	61	52	58	65
	250	36	34	37	35
	200	22	22	25	39
	125	9	10	12	31

*ti = Total inhibition.

Results and Discussion

All the sulphonamidobenzimidazole derivatives showed considerable antibacterial activity against all the microorganisms tested. Incorporation of peptide moiety into the sulphonamidobenzimidazoles resulted in higher antibacterial activity. *p*-Toluenesulphonyl derivatives were found to be more active than the corresponding benzenesulphonyl derivatives. Of the two isomeric benzimidazole derivatives, *viz.*

2-[*N*-*p*-toluenesulphonylamino]methylbenzimidazole and 2-[*N*-benzenesulphonylamino]ethylbenzimidazole, the former was more active against all the four bacteria than the latter. Higher antibacterial action of *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivatives over those of the corresponding and isomeric benzenesulphonyl derivatives may be due to closer structural analogy of the former series of compounds with *p*-aminobenzoic acid, a precursor in the biosynthesis of folic acid which is an essential constituent for bacterial growth. Though sulphonamide and other substituted sulphonamides are wellknown for their antibacterial activities^{13,14}, the benzenesulphonyl- and *p*-toluenesulphonylamino acid derivatives from which the active sulphonamidobenzimidazole derivatives (compounds 1-6) were derived, were found to be inactive against all the four bacteria. Amino acid groups probably functioned as micro-nutrients for the bacteria and thereby reduced the antibacterial actions of the corresponding sulphonamide derivatives.

Of the two other benzimidazole derivatives (compounds 7 and 8) containing the peptide moiety, the one (compound 8) having unsaturated C=C linkage showed more activity than the corresponding saturated one (compound 7). Antibacterial properties of these benzimidazole derivatives have been found to be profoundly modified in the presence of metal ions, such as Co^{++} , Ni^{++} , Cu^{++} and Zn^{++} . Results of such study will be presented in due course.

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